

The ANTARES Time-Domain Event Broker

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The astronomical community is in the midst of a revolution in Time-Domain Astronomy. The age of serendipitous discoveries of a few objects that were followed by a handful of astronomers is well in the past. Wide-field telescopes with large-format CCDs have enabled time-domain surveys that cover hundreds to thousands of square degrees every night. Digital image subtraction provides an automated pathway to finding all objects that have changed in brightness or position in any given image. The Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF) produces several hundred thousand public time-domain alerts (notifications) each night through the portion of their survey funded by NSF. The Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) will conduct a wide, fast, and deep survey of the southern sky that should generate several million alerts per night. This scale of alerts will require automated tools to filter the stream so that astronomers can find the specific objects of interest to them.

In addition, the advent of multi-messenger astronomy brings with it the promise of whole new areas of astrophysics where electromagnetic counterparts will be invaluable sources of information. Multi-messenger events usually have poor localizations on the sky, often tens to even thousands of square degrees, meaning that there will be hundreds or thousands of potential candidates for electromagnetic counterparts. Rapid identification of these counterparts will also require automated filtering systems.

A team of scientists and engineers at NOIRLab's Community Science and Data Center, along with researchers in the University of Arizona's Department of Computer Science, have been developing a software system to process and filter time-domain alerts. These tools are typically referred to as brokers as they sit between the producers of alerts and the consumers, while adding value. Our broker is the Arizona-NOIRLab Temporal Analysis and Response to Events System (ANTARES). We released v1.0 of ANTARES in June 2020, and it is currently processing the public portion of the ZTF alert stream. Access to the system and instructions for use can be found on the [ANTARES website](#).

ANTARES ingests alerts from ZTF using a streaming technology that LSST intends to employ. Each alert is checked against our internal database to determine whether or not this astrophysical source has been seen before. If not, a new source is created, and we then check multiwavelength catalogs of objects to see if this alert can be associated with any of them. These associations are attached to the alert. If ANTARES has seen an alert at this location before, the

Figure 1. The ANTARES website. Users can browse alerts, examine the pipeline, look at filters, create watch lists, search for alerts, and mark favorite alerts. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

information in the current alert is added to the history that we already have, including catalog associations.

Once alerts have associated history or known objects, ANTARES then evaluates them based on the features in the alert, from the associated objects, or from the full light curve of the source. Each of these evaluations is a filter, a short piece of Python code that runs on alerts in real time. Once filters have flagged an alert for some criterion, those alerts can be accessed as a separate, smaller stream. Filters can be as simple as finding alerts brighter than a certain threshold or alerts that occur within M31. They can also be complex, such as filters that use machine learning to classify objects based on the shape of their light curves. They can even be dynamic, as our LIGO filter must recognize new detections of gravitational wave sources and then identify

new alerts that fall within the footprint of the LIGO detection. Most important, though, is that filters can be user created. Anyone who has an idea about how to identify transient or variable sources of interest can write a filter to implement that idea, and we can then deploy that filter on the alert stream. You can get the subset of the alert stream that you want using ANTARES.

In addition to filtering the alert stream, ANTARES allows users to monitor objects for activity through watch lists. Users can upload a file with coordinates of objects of interest, and then any time there is an alert associated with one of those objects, they will be notified. Currently, this notification goes through the ANTARES Slack channel, so the level of intrusiveness for the notification is completely configurable.

At the ANTARES website (Figure 1), users can browse through recent alerts from ZTF or search for alerts of interest. Each alert page (Figure 2) displays an interactive light curve of the object along with the filters that have flagged that alert. There are also links to external astronomical data repositories. From the website, users can also manage their watch lists, select and follow favorite alerts, and create filters (via a development kit on the [NOIRLab Astro Data Lab website](#)). In addition, one can see the overall state of the ANTARES pipeline.

The ANTARES team is already producing scientific results with the system. We have authored more than 30 Astronomer’s Telegrams with classifications of transients. We’ve also reported on the discovery of the first R Corona Borealis star in the public ZTF stream [1] as well as observations of a tidal-disruption event [2]. Soraisam et al. [3] have presented an algorithm to detect anomalies in time-domain streams that we are testing within ANTARES.

The current implementation of ANTARES can process alerts at the scale produced by ZTF. Our tests indicate that our choices of technology for ANTARES will scale to the LSST production rate with a commensurate increase in CPUs and data storage. We are currently evaluating the

options for increasing our resources, including cloud-based solutions. ANTARES is a containerized system, so we can deploy to, and operate on, a wide array of data centers. We look forward to the challenges and promise that the LSST alert stream will bring.

The most valuable input we can receive right now is how you, the user, would like to see the system operate. Our goal is a world-class, community-driven broker. Let us know how we can help you do fantastic time-domain science.

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References

- [1] [Lee, C.-H., et al. 2020, AJ, 159, 61](#)
- [2] [Lee, C.-H., et al. 2020, ApJL, 892, L1](#)
- [3] [Soraisam, M. D., et al. 2020, ApJ, 892, 112](#)

Figure 2. Page for an individual object, ZTF18abdbdwz. It plots the light curve and location of alerts as well as contextual imagery from other surveys. The page links to information in other catalogs about this object and provides a finder chart to support follow-up observation. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)